

Ghost pearlite as a transient state in a high-strength Fe-Mn-C steel

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1. Supplementary Material

The synchrotron XRD diffraction pattern of the initial pearlite is depicted in Figure S1. All peaks were either attributed to α or θ . No other carbides were found.

Figure S1: Transmission XRD patterns of the initial pearlite. The intensity is plotted as a function of $2\theta_d$. Characteristic diffraction peaks corresponding to α are marked in purple, while peaks associated with θ are highlighted in brown. All relevant peaks of θ are highlighted below the spectra, while the $(211)_\theta$ and $(112)_\theta$ peaks were used to uniquely identify the carbide. Note that due to the orthorhombic unit cell of θ individual sets of planes are indexed, while for cubic α the respective families of planes are indexed. The difference is highlighted by utilizing different parentheses.

Figure S2 shows the intermediate microstructure stage STA100 between pearlite and ghost pearlite with a pearlite fraction of (0.22 ± 0.08) , that occurs if quenching is performed prior to complete transformation to γ . The time interval between onset and completion of γ transformation is expected to be dependent on pearlite colony size.

Figure S2: SEM-BSE micrograph (Nital etching) of STA100, comprising both pearlite (dark regions) and ghost pearlite (bright regions). Lamellar morphology is marked by red, fibrous by yellow arrows.

The micrographs in Figure S3 reveal the low contrast between the γ and α' lamellae in ghost pearlite, effectively inhibiting the determination of quantities like phase fractions and true interface spacing via conventional SEM, or, in the case of Figure S3 b), ion microscopy.

Figure S3: a) shows a SEM-SE micrograph (Nital etching) of STA400, comprising both ghost pearlite and conventional $\alpha' + \gamma$, while b) depicts a cross sectional micrograph of that region. Imaging the cross section was done with the ion beam at 30 kV and 26 pA. Lamellar morphology is marked by red, fibrous by yellow arrows.

Figure S4 shows a lamellar region in a) and a fibrous region in b) within the same pearlite colony. The fibers appear larger in their cross section compared to the lamellae and exhibit an inhomogeneous interface spacing.

Figure S4: a) and b) show SEM-SE micrographs of a lamellar and a fibrous region of the same pearlite colony.

Figure S5 shows an example of whole pattern refinements of the STA150 diffraction patterns before and after compression in a) and b), respectively. Due to non-random orientation, a spherical harmonics approach was used. The derived quantities, i.e. lattice constants, $c_{\alpha'}/a_{\alpha'}$ and γ fractions are given in Table S1 and show good agreement with the data presented in the main article, which were derived by fitting multiple individual peaks.

Figure S5: Neutron diffraction patterns and corresponding whole pattern Rietveld refinements of an undeformed and deformed STA150 sample in a) and b), respectively. Non-random orientation was addressed via a spherical harmonics approach.

Table S1: Summary of lattice parameters a_i , $c_{\alpha'}$, the ratio $c_{\alpha'}/a_{\alpha'}$ and phase fractions f_i for a phase i before and after deformation for samples in STA150 condition. The data was determined via a whole pattern refinement of ex-situ neutron diffraction data, which are shown in Figure S5: Neutron diffraction patterns and corresponding whole pattern Rietveld refinements of an undeformed and deformed STA150 sample in a) and b), respectively. Non-random orientation was addressed via a spherical harmonics approach.

	Strain	Phase	Lattice constants			Volume fraction
			a_i	$c_{\alpha'}$	$c_{\alpha'}/a_{\alpha'}$	
	ϵ_{total}	i	a_i	$c_{\alpha'}$	$c_{\alpha'}/a_{\alpha'}$	f_i
	%			Å		
STA150	0	γ	3.592	—	—	0.25
		α'	2.862	2.922	1.021	0.75
	11.2	γ	3.591	—	—	0.08
		α'	2.863	2.900	1.013	0.92

Figure S6 shows the dissolution of a lamellar Mn profile as solid lines and of a fibrous profile as dotted lines. The underlying assumption is that fiber radius and lamellar thickness are equal in the initial condition.

Figure S6: DICTRA simulations on the dissolution of 1D Mn concentration profiles at 770 °C. Solid and dotted lines are simulated profiles for lamellar and fibrous morphology, respectively. Both share the same thickness of 12 nm and θ spacing of $s_{\theta} = 200$ nm. The volume fraction was adjusted so the overall composition of the simulation cells amount to approximately $\bar{x}_{\text{Mn}} = 4.9$ at. % and $\bar{x}_{\text{C}} = 2.7$ at. %.

Figure S7 a) and b) show 1D C concentration profiles of STA150 and STA400 with corresponding DICTRA simulations, respectively. Additionally, corresponding DICTRA simulations are depicted.

Figure S7: DICTRA simulations (dot-dashed lines) and experimental 1D C concentration profiles (solid lines) for a) STA150 in blue and c) STA400 in orange.

An example of micrographs before and after deformation of the STA400 condition is given in Figure S8 a) and b), respectively. No microstructural-related indicators for non-uniform deformation were found, neither for the ghost pearlite nor the homogeneous $\gamma + \alpha'$ domains.

Figure S8: SEM-BSE micrographs (Nital etching) of STA400: a) before and b) after deformation to $\sim 11\%$ plastic strain. No significant changes in the respective ghost pearlite and homogeneous $\gamma + \alpha'$ domains were observed.